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TERMS AND TERMINOLOGY: CONCEPTS, FORMATION, AND STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the essence, formation stages, and development processes of the concepts of term and terminology from a scientific and theoretical perspective. The role of terms in science, technology, politics, and other specialized fields, as well as their lexical-semantic and functional features, are highlighted. Particular attention is paid to the importance of terminology in linguistics and to such characteristics of terms as systematicity, monosemy, and emotional neutrality. The article examines the scientific views on terminology proposed by scholars such as A.A. Reformatskiy, Helmut Felber, S.V. Grinev-Grinevskiy, D. Lotte, and A. Gerd. In addition, the article discusses methods of term formation, borrowing from other languages, the role of terminology in the development of scientific language, and the enrichment of terminological systems. The study concludes that terminology is an important linguistic phenomenon closely connected with scientific thinking and social development.

Keywords: term, terminology, scientific language, specialized vocabulary, terminological system, lexical-semantic features, monosemy, nominative function, term formation, borrowed terms, scientific style, language of science, diplomatic terms, linguistics, terminological units.

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada termin va terminologiya tushunchalarining mohiyati, shakllanish bosqichlari hamda rivojlanish jarayonlari ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Terminlarning ilm-fan, texnika, siyosat va boshqa maxsus sohalardagi o‘rni, ularning leksik-semantik va funksional xususiyatlari yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, terminologiyaning tilshunoslikdagi ahamiyati, terminlarning tizimlilik, bir ma’noilik va emotsional neytrallik kabi belgilariga e’tibor qaratiladi. Maqolada A.A. Reformatskiy, Helmut Felber, S.V. Grinev-Grinevskiy, D. Lotte, A. Gerd kabi

olimlarning terminologiyaga oid ilmiy qarashlari tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, terminlarning yasash usullari, boshqa tillardan o‘zlashuvi, ilmiy til rivojidadagi o‘rni hamda terminologik tizimning boyish jarayonlari haqida fikr yuritiladi. Tadqiqot natijasida terminologiya ilmiy tafakkur va jamiyat taraqqiyoti bilan chambarchas bog‘liq bo‘lgan muhim til hodisasi ekanligi asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: termin, terminologiya, ilmiy til, maxsus leksika, terminologik tizim, leksik-semantik xususiyatlar, bir ma’nodlilik, nominativ funksiyasi, termin yasash, o‘zlashma terminlar, ilmiy uslub, fan tili, diplomatik terminlar, tilshunoslik, terminologik birliklar.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье с научно-теоретической точки зрения анализируются сущность, этапы формирования и процессы развития понятий термина и терминологии. Освещается роль терминов в науке, технике, политике и других специализированных сферах, а также их лексико-семантические и функциональные особенности. Особое внимание уделяется значению терминологии в языкознании и таким признакам терминов, как системность, однозначность и эмоциональная нейтральность. В статье анализируются научные взгляды на терминологию таких ученых, как А.А. Реформатский, Helmut Felber, S.V. Grinev-Grinevskiy, D. Lotte и A. Gerd. Кроме того, рассматриваются способы образования терминов, процессы заимствования из других языков, роль терминологии в развитии научного языка и пути обогащения терминологических систем. В результате исследования обосновывается, что терминология является важным языковым явлением, тесно связанным с развитием научного мышления и общества.

Ключевые слова: термин, терминология, научный язык, специальная лексика, терминологическая система, лексико-семантические особенности, однозначность, номинативная функция, терминообразование, заимствованные термины, научный стиль, язык науки, дипломатические термины, языкознание, терминологические единицы.

In the 21st century, the emergence of new terminological units as a result of developments in science, engineering, and technology, as well as political changes, is regarded as a natural process. The necessity of deeply studying and researching this process is increasing day by day. In the field of linguistics, terms and terminology are considered important objects of research and are widely studied as significant components of language development.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of “term” is defined as follows: “Term (from the Latin *terminus* — boundary, limitation) is a word or word combination that expresses a precise and stable concept related to science, technology, professions, and other specialized fields; in other words, a technical term.”

Modern scholars such as S.V. Grinev-Grinevskiy interpret a term as a linguistic unit that expresses a precise concept within a specialized field of knowledge and possesses a strictly defined meaning.¹

Issues related to terminology have always been at the center of linguistic studies. They play an important role in determining the place and function of terms within the lexical layers of various fields, as well as in correctly understanding the content and essence of concepts. Research devoted to terminology shows that every field has its own specific terminology, which serves to express specialized concepts and perform a nominative function.

A.A. Reformatskiy explains this concept as follows: “A term is a word distinguished by its unique and specialized features; it is a precise and unambiguous word used in the fields of science, technology, economics, politics, and diplomacy. It is free from expressiveness and is characterized by strict semantic boundaries and clear definitions that explain a specific object or concept.”²

On the other hand, Helmut Felber puts forward the following idea: according to him, the word “terminology” has three different meanings:

1. Terminology is an interdisciplinary science that studies specialized concepts, signs, and the methods of their expression.
2. Terminology is a collection of terms that express a system of concepts related to specialized fields.
3. Terminology is the dissemination and promotion of specialized field concepts expressed through terms.³

From the views presented above, it can be concluded that there is no single universal definition of the word *term*. Representatives of different scientific disciplines define this concept according to their own approaches and perspectives. P. Nishonov defines a term as follows: “A term is a lexical unit in the form of a word or a word combination whose semantics are restricted to a specific field of specialization and which expresses a concept related to that particular field.”⁴

¹ S.V. Grinev-Grinevskiy. *Terminovedenie* [Terminology Studies]. Moscow: Logos, 2008, pp. 13–20.

² A.A. Reformatskiy. *Vvedenie v yazykoznanie* [Introduction to Linguistics]. Moscow, 1996, p. 61.

³ Felber H. Terminological work and standardization. –Paris. 1974, 1 p.

⁴ Nishonov P. *Comparative-typological Study of French and Uzbek Legal Terminology* (PhD dissertation). Tashkent, 2009, p. 17.

In *The World Encyclopedia Dictionary*, published in the United States in the 1970s, terminology is defined as “specialized words used in the fields of science, art, business, and economics.”¹

As the analysis demonstrates, the concept of a *term* has been interpreted in various ways by scholars and researchers. In particular, A.V. Kalinin refers to words used in specialized sciences, professions, and particular fields as *specialized vocabulary* and divides them into two categories:

1. Terms, which constitute the primary component of specialized vocabulary.
2. Professionalisms, which are also included in specialized vocabulary alongside terms.

According to Kalinin, the difference between terms and professionalisms is that “a term is a word that expresses a scientific, official, and standardized concept, whereas a professionalism is an informal expression specific to a profession that lacks a scientific foundation.”² R. Doniyorov disagrees with this viewpoint, arguing that “such rigid statements demonstrate a limitation to certain scholarly perspectives and do not fully reflect the complexity of the issue.”³

E. Wright and G. Budin identified several key areas related to terminology, including scientific and technical translation, scientific and technical communication, standardization, information exchange and information management systems, as well as the regulation of scientific relations and the systematization of language in both monolingual and multilingual environments.⁴

The development and enrichment of terminology occur through various processes, including borrowing words from other languages, creating new lexical units, the lexicalization of grammatical categories, and the semantic integration of word combinations into unified concepts. At present, Uzbek terminology is enriched primarily through language borrowing and internal word-formation processes. The stability of a terminological system in any field depends on its consistency and standardization. Therefore, the study of terminology, its structure, and its distinctive features remains a relevant issue in linguistics as well as in other scientific disciplines.

It should also be noted that the publication of specialized dictionaries plays a significant role in the development of terminology. Dictionaries are essential for ensuring the consistent and unified use of terms within a particular field of study. Furthermore, since science is constantly evolving, the emergence of new terms is a

¹ Stein, J. (Ed.). *The World Encyclopedia Dictionary*. New York: Funk & Wagnalls. 1971, 1475 p.

² A.V. Kalinin. *Lexicon of the Russian Language: Textbook*. 5th ed., revised and enlarged. Moscow: FLINTA, 2012, p. 141.

³ R. Doniyorov. *Some Issues of Uzbek Technical Terminology*. Tashkent: Fan, 1977, pp. 50–55.

⁴ Wright E., Budin G. *Handbook of Terminology Management./Volume 1: basic Aspects of Terminology Management*. – Amsterdam. Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company. 1997.1 p.

natural process. Specialized dictionaries serve as an important means of disseminating new knowledge and scientific discoveries to the broader community.

According to E. Hasanov, the language of science exists alongside colloquial speech and the language of literature as one of the functional varieties of the standard literary language.¹

The language of science is formed and develops on the basis of a nation's standard literary language. Therefore, the foundation of scientific language consists of the vocabulary, word-formation patterns, and grammatical structures of the general literary language. According to H. Whewell, terminology is the collection of terms related to a particular scientific discipline or the words used within a technical field. By identifying and recording the meanings of terms, we also identify and record the concepts they represent.²

The concept of a *term* can be understood in different ways. For example, in logic, a term is regarded as a word that denotes and is applied to a specific object through a set of defining characteristics or attributes. In principle, any word in any language can function as a term.

In the fields of science and technology, a term is a specialized word that is either deliberately coined or adopted from natural language. The scope and usage of such words are defined or restricted by representatives of particular scientific schools. Unlike general vocabulary, scientific and technical terms form interconnected terminological systems as systematic units, and their meanings are determined within these systems. Within a terminological system, the meaning of a term is closely associated with a logical and conceptual framework.

It is important to distinguish between *terms* and *terminological vocabulary*. Terms are used only within a specific terminological system and function in a specialized style related to a particular sphere of human activity. Terminological vocabulary, on the other hand, includes words and expressions that have moved beyond narrow specialization and entered broader communication and usage. Once a term becomes part of the general literary language, it gradually loses its connection with its original terminology, terminological field, and system, thereby losing some of its terminological characteristics.

According to Grigory Vinokur, a term is always precise and unambiguous. Terminological systems are consciously created and developed because terms do not

¹ Hasanov E.O. "A Study of Some Business Terms in English and Uzbek Languages." In: *Science and Technology in the Modern World*, Proceedings of the Scientific-Practical Conference, 2023, pp. 22–25.

² Whewell W. *The philosophy of the inductive sciences founded upon their history*. Vo. I-II. - London, 1967. 32 p.

emerge spontaneously without reason; rather, they arise when there is a social or scientific need for them.¹

Terminology is a collection of terms associated with the development of science and technology, and its formation and evolution occur through the emergence of specific scientific concepts. Terms arise at different stages of scientific development and gain significance as components of a particular terminological system. A term derives its meaning within that system, and outside it, the term may lose part or all of its precise meaning.

According to A. Gerd, a term is a natural or artificial linguistic unit that possesses a specific terminological meaning at a particular stage of scientific development. It consists of a word or a word combination that accurately and comprehensively reflects the essential characteristics of a scientific concept.² This is one of the key features that distinguishes terms from ordinary lexical units. Furthermore, H. Dadaboev, analyzing the views of O. Akhmanova, argues that terminology emerges only when a field of science reaches a high level of development. According to this perspective, terminology is formed and accepted through concepts that have acquired a clear scientific expression and definition.³

Terms play an important role in the research process, and their specialized meanings define scientific concepts. According to V.G. Gak, a term does not belong only to the category of special words; rather, it can be considered a type of lexical unit. Terms are not only words that perform a specific function, but they can also be viewed as one of the forms of general lexical units.⁴

In society, any new process or change is initially manifested through terminology. From this it follows that the development of terms is closely connected with important social processes. Accordingly, terminology is not only a system of scientific terms but also a specific linguistic system that reflects phenomena occurring in society.

D. Lotte proposes viewing terminology not as a separate system of signs, but within a system of concepts. According to him, terms have a systemic character and acquire full meaning only when they are connected with other concepts within the same

¹ Grigory Vinokur. "On Some Phenomena of Word Formation in Russian Technical Terminology." *Proceedings of MIFLI. Collection of Articles on Linguistics*. Moscow, 1961, pp. 3–10.

² A. Gerd. "The Meaning of the Term and Scientific Knowledge." *Scientific and Technical Information, Series 2*, Moscow, 1991, No. 10, pp. 1–4.

³ Dadaboev H. *Uzbek Terminology*. 2021, p. 7.

⁴ V.G. Gak. "Asymmetry of the Linguistic Sign and Some General Problems of Terminology (Semantic Problems of Scientific Language)." *Proceedings of the Scientific Symposium*. Moscow: Moscow State University, 1972, pp. 68–71.

system. Therefore, the position and status of each term are determined by its relation to other concepts within that system.¹

In modern linguistics, there are various views regarding the creation of new terms and the requirements imposed on them. In defining terms, their substantial, functional, derivational, and semantic aspects are taken into account.

According to the substantial approach, terms are characterized by precision, monosemy, and emotional neutrality, which distinguishes them from other words. The functional approach, however, views terms not as special words, but as words performing a specific function, suggesting that any word can potentially fulfill this role.

The processes of term formation constitute an important part of scientific language, and their fundamental difference from ordinary words has been widely studied by linguists. Terms are closely connected with the need to express new realities that emerge with the development of scientific knowledge. Each new term is created with its own specific functional nature and serves to express concepts related to a particular branch of knowledge. At the same time, every term has a clearly defined meaning and differs significantly from commonly used vocabulary.

The primary and most important feature of terms is monosemy. This means that a term expresses only one concept, and its meaning does not overlap with other words. As a result, terms form a stylistically neutral layer of scientific language and are fully and precisely understood only within their respective fields. Scholars such as U. Tursunov and K. Musayev, as well as foreign linguists like Helmut Felber and A. Gerd, have studied these characteristics in detail.²

At the same time, terminology is the process of naming concepts in scientific and technical language, and it finds its place within specialized fields. Terminological vocabulary is stylistically neutral, which means that it is free from emotional and expressive elements. This distinguishes it from ordinary literary vocabulary. Researchers in terminology emphasize that terms have a clear nominative function and operate as an organized system only within their respective fields.

Linguists consider the creation of new terms to be a creative process, as every scientific and technical term is specifically formed to express an exact concept. However, no language can fully develop its terminology solely through its own lexical resources. Therefore, borrowing terms from other languages is regarded as a natural

¹ D.S. Lotte. *Fundamentals of the Construction of Scientific and Technical Terminology: Issues of Theory and Methodology*. Moscow, 1961, p. 29.

² U. Tursunov. *Scientific Style and Its Linguistic Means*. Tashkent: Fan, 1985, p. 27.

K. Musayev. *Issues of Language and Terminology*. Tashkent: Fan, 1979, p. 45.

Helmut Felber. *Terminology Manual*. Paris: UNESCO, 1984, p. 12.

A. Gerd. *Fundamentals of Terminology Studies*. Moscow: Nauka, 2001, p. 36.

V.V. Vinogradov. *On the Language of Scientific Prose*. Moscow: Nauka, 1968, pp. 120–125.

process. Nevertheless, such borrowing must be based on necessity; otherwise, artificial adoption of terms may not be effective. For example, the introduction of foreign terms whose meanings are not clearly understood often hinders the popularization of scientific concepts.

In conclusion, every language, including scientific language, is in a constant process of change and development. Terminology is a key part of this process, serving as the main tool for expressing new concepts. Therefore, scientific language continuously expands through the creation of new terms, contributing to the overall development of language.

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